

PROPHYLACTIC PROBLEMS IN THE PREVENTION OF INFECTIOUS DISEASES
IN ANIMALS

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Resume. *This article mainly deals with the scientific analysis of the emergence of diseases in the animal world and its prevention. Proposals and recommendations on their content and prevention are given.*

Keywords. *animal world, development, system, prevention, activity, sick animal, dispensation, body structure, diagnosis, diseases, pericarditis, reticulitis, treatment.*

The animal world is considered the most important unique nature of the general development system. It is very necessary to carry out preventive activities of the animal world. For this reason, it is advisable to pay serious attention to the aspects that we offer below in order to prevent any diseases in the animal scientist.

Every sick animal should be registered first when it is brought to the treatment facility. In order to quickly and accurately find a sick animal among other animals, identifying and recording its unique individual characteristics is called animal recording or registration. When registering an animal, the necessary information is requested from the animal's owner or the person who takes care of it, and depending on the submitted documents, the animal is examined in general.[1] This is transferred to the animal registration journal, medical history, dispensary card. In this case, the time the animal arrived at the hospital, the name, surname and residence of the animal owner, the type, sex, age, breed, color and some signs of the animal, nickname or ring number, obesity, behavior, body structure or constitution, time of illness, diagnosis, the result of treatment and the time of discharge from the treatment facility are written.

By determining the type of animal, we mean which diseases are more common in animals of this type. For example, most ungulates have manka and dumb (sap, myt); traumatic pericarditis, reticulitis, dangerous catarrhal fever, black fever in cattle; diseases of saramas (roja) and atrophic rhinitis occur in pigs. When choosing drugs for treatment, it is necessary to take into account the sensitivity of certain species of animals to certain drugs. For example, ruminant animals are very sensitive to mercury preparations, cats to phenol.[2] Purebred animals are more susceptible to disease than non-breed animals, and the disease is severe. For example, purebred dogs are less susceptible to plague than purebred dogs. Some diseases occur only in male animals, while others occur only in females. Slaughtering male animals also has a certain effect on the performance of the animal. The age of the animal depends on the resistance of the body and susceptibility to certain diseases. The size and fatness of the animal is necessary when determining the dose of the medicine. In addition, registration data is considered a legal document, used for making monthly, quarterly and annual reports, for diagnosis. Therefore, the information on the registration of sick animals should be written clearly, comprehensibly and completely.

Anamnesis (from the Greek anamnesis - means to remember) is to ask the owner or the person who cares about the animal's life and illness before coming to the hospital. Thus, when collecting anamnesis information, the doctor asks the owner of the animal or a person who cares for it about its life and illness, and they answer the questions by recalling it. That is, the anamnesis is a conversation between the doctor and the owner of the animal. Collecting anamnesis data is of great importance for the doctor to diagnose the disease, and it is important for identifying some diseases. Therefore, when collecting the anamnesis data, the

doctor should have a friendly, good conversation with the owner of the animal and find out all the information that the owner of the animal knows. The doctor's questions should be understandable for the owner of the animal or the person taking care of it. Sometimes, if the animal gets sick due to the fault of the person taking care of the animal - the cowherd or the calf, he may give the wrong answer.[3] Therefore, the information obtained during the anamnesis is compared with the results of the examination and it is determined whether it is correct or incorrect. In addition to these, other veterinary staff are also asked when the anamnesis information is obtained, and the submitted documents are reviewed.

Information about the life of an animal - Anamnesis vitae. When asked about the life of an animal, the following questions are answered:

1. Origin of the animal: was the sick animal born and raised in the owner's house or was it bought? If he was born and raised at home, information about his parents will be requested. If purchased: when, where and from whom? Are there diseases in the purchased farm?

2. Conditions of keeping the animal: where is the animal kept, in a room, under a porch, or outdoors? If it is in a room, the building's floor, ventilation, lighting, heating or cooling are requested. Is the animal kept alone or with a group; connected or open? Will the asset receive a loan, will it be released? How many times is the animal inside the building cleaned? It is asked about the excretion of manure and urine.

3. Animal feeding and watering conditions; how many times they are fed, what kind of food is given; quantity and quality of food provided; whether food is given at the end or not; alone - alone or with a group; whether the given food is rotten, moldy; no poison ivy? Are minerals, table salt, vitamins added to the diet? Where is the animal watered: from a water pipe, a well, a stream, a lake, a pond, a canal, a river, etc. What is the quality and temperature of the supplied water, how is it transported and supplied?

4. It is determined whether the animal is pregnant, has given birth, or has an infected udder.

5. It is determined for what purpose the animal is kept (for production, breeding, labor, hobby, teaching, etc.).

Determining the size of the animal. For this, attention is paid to the development of the bones and muscles of the animal and it is checked visually. Depending on the development of bones and muscles, the body of the animal is similar to that of a sheep. Strong-bodied animals are characterized by well-developed bones and muscles. Such animals have a large and heavy head, a short and thick neck, a wide and developed chest, short and thick legs, wide joints and a narrow waist. Their lungs, heart and intestines are well developed, and they are more resistant to the bad effects of the external environment. Although such animals are quite resistant to diseases, they are prone to certain diseases (ketosis, myoglobinuria, postpartum paresis and other diseases). Medium-bodied animals have moderately developed body bones and muscles, and such animals are productive and resistant to diseases. Weak-bodied animals are characterized by poorly developed body bones and muscles. The head of such animals is small and light, the neck is thin and long, the chest is narrow, the legs, waist, and stomach are long and thin. Even if the spinal cord of animals is injured, they have rickets, osteodystrophy, and rheumatism, they have a weak jussa. Such animals are prone to diseases, and the disease is severe and chronic. Cattle with weak jussa often suffer from tuberculosis; calves and piglets to diseases of rickets, pneumonia, salmonellosis, paratyphoid, dictiocaulosis; horses suffer from chronic pulmonary emphysema and heart diseases. In dogs with a weak body, plague is severe and the animal often dies.

Determination of animal obesity. Fatness of the animal is determined by the accumulation of subcutaneous fat and the development of muscles. Depending on the fatness of the animal, the type and quality of feeding, the level of metabolism is determined. If the farm animals are fed correctly and of good quality, their fatness is good, if they are fed poorly and poorly, their fatness is bad, the animal is thin. During diseases, the moisture content of the skin can change:

1. Animal sweating or hyperhidrosis. This condition often occurs in horses, and sometimes in ruminants. Normally, when the outside temperature is too high, when the animals are left under the sun, when the air humidity increases, general sweating is also observed when working. Pathological general sweating is observed in severe and severe fever, myoglobinuria, during colic, severe pain, heart disease, uremia, during shivering, when injecting pilocarpine, adrenaline and salicylic drugs into the body.

2. Limited or localized sweating (hypohidrosis) - in which the skin and wool in some places are covered with sweat drops. This condition can be observed during mechanical injury of the peripheral nerve, inflammation and injury of the spinal cord. Strong sweating of the stomach area in horses is a sign of stomach rupture. Bloody sweat may appear if the skin bleeds (hemohidrosis).

3. Dryness of the skin (anhidrosis) - is observed when the formation of sweat on the skin is reduced or absent at all. This condition can occur when the body is dehydrated, thin, in diabetes, in nephritic diseases, and in fever. On dry skin, wool is snoring, and at this time, the nasal cavity, nose of dogs and cats is dry. On palpation, the skin is dry, hot and cracked, and many crusts appear on the surface of the skin. In case of stomach-intestinal diseases of cattle, the drops of sweat are small and do not form again immediately after wiping the sweat. Therefore, the size of the sweat drops is also taken into account during the examination.

Skin temperature - by determining the temperature of the skin, it is possible to determine the pathological processes in the skin, subcutaneous tissues and internal organs, the uniform distribution of blood in the blood vessels of the skin, the release of heat, and the body temperature. The temperature of the skin depends on the thickness of the blood vessels, the amount and speed of the blood in the blood vessels, and the release of heat. Therefore, the temperature of the skin is different in different animals and in different areas of the skin.

In general, the world of animals is a part of nature, and it is everyone's duty to protect them. That is why it is necessary to pay great attention to the world of animals.

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